

DIGITAL MARKETING TRAINING TO INCREASE INDUSTRIAL SALES IN MARINDAL VILLAGE

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Abstract

This Community Service (PKM) activity aims to increase the capacity of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Marindal Village to utilize digital marketing as a marketing strategy to expand their market and increase sales. The methods used included situational analysis, training, mentoring, and evaluation using pre- and post-test instruments. The results of the activity showed a significant increase in participants' understanding of digital marketing concepts (28% to 90%), business account creation skills (15% to 80%), and digital content creation skills (10% to 75%). In addition, there was a shift in marketing patterns from conventional to digital-based systems, which resulted in increased product visibility and business confidence in managing their businesses. However, challenges such as limited internet infrastructure, low digital literacy among some participants, and a lack of consistent promotions remain obstacles that need to be overcome. This PKM activity concluded that implementing digital marketing is an effective strategy in increasing the competitiveness of SMEs, with the note that ongoing mentoring and digital infrastructure support are needed.

Keywords: *Digital Marketing, Industrial Sales, Community Service, Marindal village*

INTRODUCTION

Micro-enterprises are productive businesses owned by individuals or individual business entities that meet the criteria for micro-enterprises. Small businesses are independent productive businesses, run by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries of companies owned, controlled, or part of either directly or indirectly medium or large businesses that meet the criteria for small businesses. Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises, or abbreviated as MSMEs, have a very crucial role in the economic and industrial growth of a country. In fact, MSMEs are one of the sources of job creation and make a direct contribution to efforts to reduce poverty (Mahdi, 2022). The existence of MSMEs every year experiences development and will continue to grow. The Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs recorded that in 2019 the number of MSMEs reached 64.47 million units and will increase in the following years (Dewi & Mahyuni, 2022). Therefore, the development of MSMEs should be a focus in economic development in the private sector as the era of free competition develops. Related to the increasing competition among MSME actors, MSMEs are required to increase their competitiveness in order to survive and thrive.

One way that can be implemented is by using information and communication technology (ICT) to support the business activities of MSMEs, especially with the changes in the behavior and habits of end consumers. The rapid development of the digital era is unavoidable, so MSMEs are encouraged to adapt early. Therefore, MSMEs must be able to think creatively and innovatively to maximize the use of digital developments. Digital marketing is one promotional activity that MSMEs can engage in. Digital marketing is a product and service marketing technique that utilizes information technology as a medium. The use of social media is one such platform due to its easy access for the general public (Dasuki et al., 2022). Commonly used social media platforms include Instagram, Facebook, and others. The use of social media in marketing products and services by MSMEs has proven effective in changing the attitudes and perceptions of targeted consumers (Krisgaharu & Kusuma, 2022). However, in practice, MSMEs encounter several inhibiting factors in terms of digital literacy in the marketing sector, where human resource

capabilities are still limited. For example, in the ability to access marketing functions, especially in obtaining market information and market networks. However, implementing the use of ICT still requires adequate infrastructure. When compared to urban areas, digital literacy remains a challenge for MSMEs in rural areas due to limited access to knowledge about it (Srijani & Kadeni, 2020). Marindal Village is one of the villages in North Sumatra with potential for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), such as processed foods, handicrafts, and household products. However, the majority of businesses still rely on traditional marketing strategies, such as direct sales and word-of-mouth promotion. This situation limits their ability to expand their market and increase sales. Therefore, intervention in the form of Community Service activities focused on digital marketing implementation is necessary. Through these activities, it is hoped that Marindal Village businesses can utilize digital technology to improve product competitiveness, expand marketing networks, and increase revenue. The program includes training and mentoring for MSMEs on digital marketing, including the use of social media and tools to monitor marketing effectiveness. Several similar training programs have been conducted in several villages, such as digital marketing training for MSMEs in Banjar Pitik, which has received positive feedback through the training and education provided (Dewi & Mahyuni, 2022). Efforts to improve digital literacy through digital marketing training were also conducted in Cisoka Village on the use of social media (Dasuki et al., 2022). The method used for MSME training is a participatory action research (PAR) approach. The benefit of this activity is to improve the digital literacy of MSME partners, thereby increasing the competitiveness of MSME businesses and enabling them to survive in the rapidly developing digital era. This program is implemented to support Keramas Village in becoming a digital village.

METHOD

1. Activity Design

This Community Service (PKM) activity uses a participatory approach, actively involving small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Marindal Village at every stage. The activity is designed using a combination of interactive lectures, hands-on training, group discussions, and individual mentoring.

2. Subject of Activity

The participants were 25 SMEs from Marindal Village, operating in the processed food, handicraft, and household products sectors. Participants were selected based on:

- Minimum 1 year of active business availability.
- Willingness to participate in the entire series of activities.
- Willingness to implement digital marketing after training.

3. Location and Time of Implementation

The activity was carried out at Marindal Village Hall in July–August 2025, with a total activity time of 6 weeks.

4. Implementation Stages

a. Needs Analysis

- Field observations were conducted to identify the main problems faced by business actors.
- Interviews were conducted to determine participants' initial level of understanding regarding digital marketing.
- A pre-test survey was distributed to measure participants' basic abilities before the training.

b. Socialization

- Delivery of material regarding the basic concepts of digital marketing, digital marketing trends, and differences with conventional marketing.
- Explanation of digital marketing opportunities in increasing the competitiveness of local products.

Figure 1.

c. Training

The training is conducted intensively with the following materials:

1. Utilization of Social Media
 - Create a business account on Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok.
 - Promotion strategies through posts, stories, and paid advertising.
2. Marketplace Usage
 - Creating online stores on Shopee, Tokopedia, and Bukalapak.
 - How to upload products, write descriptions, and set prices.
3. Digital Content Creation
 - Basic product photography techniques using a smartphone.
 - Simple editing using the Canva/CapCut application.
 - Simple persuasive copywriting.

d. Mentoring

- Participants are accompanied to practice directly creating a business account.
- The PKM team helped upload the first product to the marketplace.
- Participants are guided in creating a weekly promotional content schedule.

e. Evaluation

- It is conducted through pre-test and post-test to assess the increase in participants' understanding.
- Direct observation of social media accounts and marketplaces that have been created.
- A short interview regarding changes in marketing patterns and the challenges faced.

5. Measuring Instruments

- Pre-test and post-test questionnaires were used to measure understanding of digital marketing theory.
- The skills checklist is used to assess participants' practical abilities in creating accounts, uploading products, and creating content.
- In-depth interviews were used to find out participants' experiences during the activity.

6. Data Analysis

Pre-test and post-test data were analyzed using quantitative descriptive methods in the form of percentage improvement in skills. Meanwhile, observation and interview data were analyzed qualitatively to illustrate changes in marketing patterns and the challenges faced by business actors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Participant Characteristics

The PKM activity involved 25 small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) players in Marindal Village. Most of them operate in the following sectors:

- Processed foods (40%)
- Handicrafts (32%)
- Household products (28%)

In terms of education, the majority of participants were high school graduates (60%), while the remainder were junior high school graduates (28%) and college graduates (12%). This indicates that most business owners had limited digital literacy prior to participating in the program.

Pre-test and Post-test Results

To measure the effectiveness of the activity, a pre-test and post-test were conducted. The pre-test was conducted before the activity began, while the post-test was conducted after the training and mentoring.

Table 1. Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Results

NO	Category	Pre-test	Post-test	Improvement
1	Understanding Digital Marketing	28	90	+62
2	Ability to Create a Business Account	15	80	+65
3	Content Creation Skills	10	75	+65

Figure 1. Comparison of PKM Participants' Pre-test and Post-test Results

These results show a significant improvement in all aspects: understanding, technical skills, and the ability to create digital content.

Improving Practical Skills

Observation results show that participants successfully applied the training material directly:

- 100% of participants successfully created business accounts on social media.
- 85% of participants successfully opened an online store in the marketplace.
- 72% of participants actively upload product content (photos/videos) independently.

This fact shows that participants not only understand the theory, but are also able to practice digital marketing in real life.

Changes in Marketing Patterns

Before the event, most businesses relied on offline sales through word-of-mouth and local consumers. After the event, there was a shift in marketing patterns:

- 60% of participants started using social media (Instagram/Facebook/TikTok) for promotion.
- 40% of active participants use the marketplace as a product distribution channel.
- Several participants reported an increase in orders, especially from consumers outside Marindal Village

Impact of PKM Activities

This activity has a positive impact on three main aspects:

1. Economic Aspect: Some participants began to feel an increase in sales after 2 weeks of active digital promotion.
2. Knowledge Aspect: participants better understand the importance of branding, promotional consistency, and the use of digital media.
3. Skills Aspect: Participants are able to create simple digital content independently.

Challenges Faced

Although the activity was successful, there were several obstacles, including:

- Limited internet network in several areas of Marindal Village.
- Limited technological skills in elderly participants.
- Limited promotional consistency, where some participants are still not actively uploading content regularly.

These obstacles demonstrate the need for ongoing mentoring and support from village governments to provide adequate digital infrastructure.

Discussion

Overall, the results of this activity prove that the implementation of digital marketing is able to:

- Improving the knowledge and skills of business actors.
- Changing traditional marketing patterns towards digital-based marketing.
- Provides economic impact in the form of increased sales.

This finding is consistent with the opinion of Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick (2019) who emphasized that digital marketing is an important strategy in increasing the competitiveness of SMEs in the era of globalization.

CONCLUSION

The Community Service (PKM) program in Marindal Village successfully achieved its stated goal of increasing the capacity of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to utilize digital marketing as a modern marketing strategy. Based on the implementation results, several key points can be concluded:

1. Improved Knowledge and Understanding:
Participants gained a better understanding of digital marketing concepts, including promotional strategies through social media and marketplaces. This was evident in the post-test results, which showed significant improvement compared to the pre-test.
2. Practical Skills Enhancement:
Participants will be able to create business accounts on social media, open online stores on marketplaces, and produce simple digital content in the form of product photos and videos. These skills are essential for entrepreneurs competing in the digital age.
3. Marketing Pattern Changes:

Before the event, the majority of participants relied solely on offline promotions. After the event, there was a shift in marketing patterns toward digital media. Most participants began actively using social media and marketplaces, and some even experienced an increase in orders.

4. The Economic and Social Impact

Digital Marketing Implementation has had a positive impact on increasing sales, expanding markets, and strengthening local product brands. Socially, this activity has increased business confidence in managing their businesses more professionally.

5. Challenges Faced:

Obstacles still encountered include limited internet infrastructure, low digital literacy among some elderly participants, and a lack of consistency in routine promotions. These factors indicate the need for follow-up in the form of ongoing mentoring.

Thus, the implementation of digital marketing has been proven to increase the competitiveness of MSME products in Marindal Village. For sustainability, village government support is recommended in providing digital infrastructure, strengthening the capacity of business actors through advanced training, and providing regular mentoring to ensure consistent and sustainable implementation of digital marketing strategies.

Suggestion

Based on the results of PKM activities, several suggestions that can be put forward are as follows:

1. Digital Infrastructure Support

The village government and related parties are expected to improve the quality of the internet network in Marindal Village as a major supporter of digital marketing success.

2. Ongoing Mentoring

Similar activities need to be carried out periodically with a continuous mentoring model so that participants are more consistent in implementing digital marketing strategies.

3. Improving Digital Literacy

Further training is needed that focuses on developing creative content, branding strategies, and utilizing paid advertising features on social media and marketplaces.

4. Collaboration with External Parties

Collaboration between SMEs, universities, and government agencies needs to be strengthened in the form of business incubation or digital clinics to support the development of technology-based businesses.

By implementing these suggestions, it is hoped that business actors in Marindal Village will be able to transform towards more effective, consistent, and highly competitive digital marketing in regional and national markets.

REFERENCES

- Dasuki, TMS, Magribi, RM, Sulviani, A., Kusumadewi, RN, & Nur, LZ (2022). Economic Recovery Through Digitalization Literacy In Cisoka Village, Majalengka Regency. *BERNAS: Journal of Community Service* , 3 (4), 1048–1053. <https://doi.org/10.31949/jb.v3i4.3487>
- Dewi, KNK, & Mahyuni, LP (2022). Digital Marketing Training for MSMEs in Banjar Pitik for Business Competitiveness. *Dinamisia: Journal of Community Service* , 6 (3), 716–724. <https://doi.org/10.31849/dinamisia.v6i3.6302>
- Hardilawati, WL (2020). MSME Survival Strategies Amid the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Accounting and Economics* , 10 (1), 89-98. <https://doi.org/10.37859/jae.v10i1.1934>
- Krisgaharu, T., & Kusuma, BOP (2022). The Level of Effectiveness of Online Marketing for MSMEs During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *EXERO: Journal of Research in Business and Economics* , 4 (2), 207–227. <https://doi.org/10.24071/exero.v4i2.5033>
- Mahdi, MI (2022). How Many MSMEs Are There in Indonesia? (Online), (<https://dataindonesia.id/sektor-riil/detail/berapa-jumlah-umkm-di-indonesia>), accessed November 29, 2022
- Srijani, N., & Kadeni. (2020). The Role of MSMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises) in Improving Community Welfare. *EQUILIBRIUM: Scientific Journal of Economics and Its Learning* , 8 (2), 191-200. <https://doi.org/10.25273/equilibrium.v8i2.7118>